

SOCIOCULTURAL DIFFERENCES IN FAMILY DISCOURSE IN FICTION BOOKS OF UZBEK LANGUAGE

Djuraeva Mukhlisa Shadiyarovna

Teacher of UzSWLU, the department of the English functional lexics

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Annotation: This article examines the sociocultural features in family discourse presented in some Uzbek fiction books. The family institution holds great significance in Uzbek culture, and exploring how it is portrayed in fiction books allows for a greater understanding of the life of Uzbek people, its complexities and nuances.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ba'zi o'zbek badiiy adabiyotlarida keltirilgan oilaviy nutqdagi ijtimoiy-madaniy xususiyatlar ko'rib chiqiladi. Oila maktabi o'zbek madaniyatida katta ahamiyatga ega bo'lib, uning badiiy adabiyotlarda qanday tasvirlanganligini o'rganish o'zbek xalqi hayoti, uning murakkabliklari va nozik tomonlarini yanada chuqurroq tushunish imkonini beradi.

Key words: Uzbek literature, Uzbek fiction books, sociocultural, family discourse.

Literature and fiction books often depict sociocultural aspects of different nations. They can provide insights into the beliefs, values, customs, traditions, and social structures of a particular society. These aspects can include elements such as family dynamics, gender roles, religious practices, political systems, economic realities, and social class hierarchies. Through storytelling and the exploration of characters and their interactions, literature provides a window into different cultures and societies, allowing readers to gain a deeper understanding of the sociocultural foundations of a nation.

In many Uzbek language fiction books, family members are portrayed as caring, supportive, and interconnected. Family relations, which have a long history are revealed in an interesting way in Uzbek artistic works. Respect for elders is evident in the way younger generations interact with their parents and grandparents. The fiction books and stories often depict multi-generational households, where older members play a central role in decision-making processes and offer guidance and wisdom to their younger counterparts.

In one of the greatest masterpieces of **Abdulla Qodiriy**, "**Bygone days**" (**O'tkan kunlar**" 1926), various human destinies, social-political, spiritual-moral, family-love problems are written. However, the issue of the country's destiny and independence stands out among them. Another important feature of the novel

"Bygone Days" is it emphasizes the national spirit of Uzbek people. This feature can be found in the interior and exterior of the images, as well as it is evident in the landscape and the plot image. Also, it gives a lot of interesting information to the reader about Uzbek people, their traditions, customs, such as waiting for guests, sending suitors, weddings and other national marriage ceremonies.

In **Abdulhamid Chulpan's novel "Night and Day" ("Kecha va kunduz" 1936)** the characteristics of family relationships, some disappearing traditions, and the qualities of the Uzbek people are vividly displayed in the social context. According to the work, we can see a man's respect for his wife in the society, by calling his wife not by her name, but by the name of her first child. In addition, women show more respect to their husbands, they do not even look their spouse in the eye; they do not do anything without their spouse's permission. This is a feature unique to Uzbek women, not found in other nations.

Another aspect of family discourse explored in Uzbek fiction books is the significance of extended family networks. It is also widely revealed in the books of Uzbek literature, which emphasize the close ties between relatives and depict the extended family as an essential support system. It is common for multiple generations to reside in close proximity, with aunts, uncles, and cousins playing an active role in raising children and providing emotional and financial support. The interdependence between family members and their commitment to each other's well-being are continuously portrayed in Uzbek literature. As an example, in **Said Ahmad's comedy book "Brides' Rebellion" ("Kelinlar Qo'zg'oloni" 1976)**, a big family is depicted, where a mother and her seven sons with their families live in one house. In "Brides' Rebellion", not only the mother-in-law and daughter-in-law problem, family disagreements, but also the sons' respect for their mothers, their loyalty, mother's unquenchable love behind anger, or the harmony of the brides helping each other is shown. The solution of family problems is shown with a light smile. In the play, the social and cultural relations typical of the Uzbek nation are revealed.

In conclusion, exploring the sociocultural differences in family discourse through Uzbek language fiction books offers valuable insights into Uzbek peoples' life. These stories present a rich tapestry of collectivism, traditional gender roles, the importance of marriage, and the significance of extended family networks. By examining these narratives, readers gain a deeper understanding of the Uzbek society's values, customs, and complexities, ultimately fostering intercultural understanding and appreciation.

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